

INGENUITY COMPARISON OF ALUMINUM DOPED COBALT FERRITE AND BARIUM DOPED COBALT FERRITE AS ANODE FOR LITHIUM - ION BATTERIES SYNTHESIZED BY SOL - GEL TECHNIQUE

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Abstract

Aluminum doped Cobalt ferrite and Barium doped Cobalt ferrite nanoparticles have been prepared successfully by the Sol-gel technique. Systematic characterization are done using Powder X-ray Diffraction, Scanning Electron Microscopy and energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy to study structural, morphological and magnetic behavior of the prepared samples. The observed diffraction patterns of Aluminum ion and Barium ion substituted CoFe_2O_4 samples show the diffraction patterns correspond to the cubic CoFe_2O_4 crystalline phase. The cubic structure indicates that the doping elements have substituted into the structure successfully. Comparing the SEM images of CoFe_2O_4 , AlCoFeO_4 and $\text{Ba}_{0.5}\text{CoFe}_{1.67}\text{O}_4$, the grains of AlCoFeO_4 are fused more than other compounds; it proves that the conductivity will be increased by replacing Fe^{3+} by Al^{3+} in CoFe_2O_4 . SEM images show a uniform but agglomerate surface of cobalt ferrite nanoparticles. Because of the very small size of the crystallites, it can be helpful in reduction and oxidation of metal nanoparticles, which in turn can enhance the capacity of anode material. The EDS values of CoFe_2O_4 , AlCoFeO_4 and $\text{Ba}_{0.5}\text{CoFe}_{1.67}\text{O}_4$ confirm the presence of Co, Fe, O, Al and Ba elements in the corresponding samples. The synthetic effects of all components result in the enhancement of lithium storage performance through accelerating the electron/ion transfer and increasing the structural and interfacial stability.

1. Introduction

In the development of science and technology, a magnetic material plays a major role. Magnetic nanoparticles have a great demand due to its novel characteristics and extensive applications in various fields. Development of new theoretical and experimental techniques offers opportunities for the development of innovative nanodevices and nanomaterials [1].

Nanotechnology is the science of understanding the structure and behavior of materials at the atomic or molecular level. The word, Nano has been derived from the Greek word 'Nanos', represent billionth fraction of a unit or 10^{-9} m [2]. Nanoscience and nanotechnology have many applications in semiconductor electronics, sensors, magnetic, advanced ceramics and membranes [3,4]. Society begins to use nanomaterials; it emerges the growth of technology [5-7].

Classification of nanoparticles is based on dimensionality, morphology, composition, uniformity and agglomeration. Shape or morphology of a nanoparticle plays an important role in their toxicity. Nanomaterials can be nano-scale in zero dimension {e.g. light emitting diodes (LEDs) [8], solar cells [9-11], single-electron transistors [12,13] and lasers [14]}, one dimension [15,16] (e.g. surface films) [17], two dimensions (e.g. strands or fibers) [18,19] or three dimensions (e.g. particles). 3-D nanostructure has a wide range of application in the area of catalysis, magnetic materials and electrode material for batteries [20-22]. Flatness, sphericity and aspects ratio are the morphological characteristics. General classifications are high-aspect-ratio particles (nanotubes, nanowires) and low-aspect-ratio particles (spherical, over, cubic) [2]. Nanoparticles can be composed of a single constituent material or be a composite of several materials. The nanoparticles found in nature are often agglomerations of materials with various compositions. Based on chemistry and their electromagnetic properties, nanoparticles can exist in dispersed aerosols, suspensions or in agglomerate state.

Physical and chemical properties of the nanomaterials depend on their size, shape or morphology. At Nanoscale, electrical conductivity and mechanical strength are not the same as they are at bulk size. These properties are utilized in the field of information storage [23], Ferro-fluids [24,25] etc.

1.2. Ferrites

Iron oxides are combined with different metal oxides, the chief component is ferrite, deduced from a Latin word "ferum" stands for 'iron in different things' [26]. Ferrites or ferromagnetic oxides are ceramic materials which are primary part of Iron oxide [27]. Ferrites are dark brown or gray in appearance and very hard and brittle in physical character. They are prepared by heat-treating various transition metal oxides or alkaline earth oxides with the ferric oxides [28]. The Ferrites are non-conducting magnetic media so eddy current and ohmic losses are less than for ferromagnetic materials. Many ferrites are spinel with the formula AB_2O_4 . The magnetic material 'ZnFe'

has the formula ZnFe_2O_4 with Fe^{3+} occupying the octahedral sites and Zn^{2+} occupies the tetrahedral sites. This material is an example of normal structure spinel ferrite.

Depending on the magnetic properties, ferrites can be categorized as 'soft' and 'hard' ferrite. Soft ferrites have low coercivity while the hard ferrites have high coercivity and moderate magnetization [29]. The ferrites exhibit dielectric properties and do not conduct electricity easily therefore ferrites became an alternative for the metal magnets like iron, nickel which conduct electricity readily. Ferrite has magnetic materials than pure metals because of their high resistivity, lower cost, easier manufacture and superior magnetization properties. Uses of ferrites are in radar, audio–video and digital recording, mechanical filter, ultrasonic generator, Recording heads (Storage devices), Transducers (ultrasonic cleaners), Optical properties (sun screen, hyper thermic cancer treatment) etc.

1.3. Introduction on batteries

- ✓ The electrical energy is stored in energy storage devices like batteries and super capacitors. The stored chemical energy is converted into electrical energy by Redox reactions.
- ✓ The batteries are classified as Primary batteries and Secondary batteries.
- ✓ In primary battery electrode reaction are not reversible. Hence, the cells are non-rechargeable. Ex. Zinc - carbon battery.
- ✓ A secondary battery, the electrode reactions are reversible, i.e., the application of external voltage can reconstruct the electrodes to their initial state. Hence, the batteries are rechargeable. The characteristics, such as capacity, cyclability, environmentally friendliness and safety issues are the important concerns in secondary rechargeable batteries. Ex. Lead-acid battery, Nickel - Cadmium (Ni-Cd) battery, Nickel-metal hydride battery.

In secondary battery, Lithium ion batteries exhibit high specific energy, energy density, individual cell potential and the self-discharge rate is low when compared to other batteries. The energy requirements and growth are linked up directly with social and economic development of human life [29]. Secondary lithium batteries is an energy storage device which has high voltage positive electrode materials, cell potential, high energy density, high capacity, long cycle life these are all due to the smaller size and lightweight of lithium [30-32]. Thus, lithium is most suitable for many portable electronic devices like cell phone, mobile computers, pacemakers as well as military equipment and hydric electric vehicles [33]. The current research of lithium ion battery is mainly to improve the battery performance with good capacity retention at high current rate and energy density to meet the current energy demands to a low cost. In 1991, lithium-ion battery was 'born' and grows up, the modern world cannot be described without it [34].

In the periodic table third element is Lithium, the most negative electrode potential and is stable only in nonaqueous electrolytes. Lithium-ion batteries are composed of three parts: anode, cathode, and electrolyte. Lithium-ion batteries consist of negative electrode and positive electrode in an electrochemical cell [35]. Lithium ion battery (LIB) is most popular and efficient with high capacity, small volume, long lifetime and high security [36-38]. Compared with other rechargeable batteries, such as lead-acid cell, nickel-cadmium cell; LIB has an impressive advantages [39]. Types of electrochemical energy storage devices (EESDs) [40] such as lithium-ion batteries [41], lithium–air batteries [42], sodium-ion batteries [43], and super capacitors [44] have attracted great attention.

1.4. Composition of lithium ion battery (LIB)

- ✓ The anode is a negative electrode and it donates electrons to the external circuit during oxidation reaction and accepts electrons from the external circuit during reduction reaction.
- ✓ The cathode is a positive electrode and it accepts electrons from the external circuit through reduction reaction.
- ✓ The electrolyte acts like a medium for ion transport between anode and cathode. The main function is to prevent electrical short circuits and at the same time allow rapid transport of ionic charge carriers that are needed to complete the circuit during the passage of current in an electrochemical cell [45, 46]. Carbon materials are widely used in lithium batteries [47].

During discharge process, lithium moves from the state of high chemical potential (high energy) in the negative electrode to the state of low chemical potential (low energy) in the positive electrode, results in work done by the cell. The involvement of energies of both electron and Li^+ ion transfer plays key role to determine voltage of a cell [48,49]. Lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) are considered as predominant power source for portable electronic devices. Advanced electrode materials with high reversible capacity, good cyclic performance and rate capability are highly desired. Among them, the spinel CoFe_2O_4 with a high theoretical capacity of 916 mAh g^{-1} has been regarded as a good choice for anode material because of the synergic effects between different metal species [50].

The current research and development of lithium ion battery is focused towards high energy applications, which include the utility of lithium ion battery in heavy electric vehicles. In order to satisfy these criteria, the developed lithium ion battery must possess high energy density as well as high power density. At high power applications, the electrode material must withstand its capacity at high current draw rates. This can be achieved by using nanoparticles and porous anode materials. Literature reports suggest that rare earth ion doped, and its oxides coated

cathode materials were used in the lithium ion battery to improve the cycle stability and improve the thermal stability.

Among all ferrite Nanoparticles, cobalt ferrite with spinel structure have attracted scientists and technologists due to its significant chemical stability, high Curie temperature, high magnetization, high electrical resistivity and negligible eddy current losses. It is useful in high frequency magnetic applications, magnetic recording applications, audio-video tapes and high-density digital discs etc. Several researchers have reported on Cd, Cr, Mn, Ti, Zn, Gd, Pr, and Nd substituted cobalt ferrite. To our knowledge, there are very few detailed studies on aluminum substituted cobalt ferrite and barium substituted cobalt ferrite $Ba_xCoFe_{2-x}O_4$ [51] (with $x = 0.0, 0.25, 0.5, 0.75$ and 1.0) synthesized by the sol-gel method.

1.5. Sol-gel technique

The magnetic ferrite particles can be synthesized by different methods such as co-precipitation, hydrothermal, sol-gel, etc [52]. One of the most popular non-conventional synthesis methods is sol-gel method [53], the technique to obtain homogenous ferrite powders with nano crystalline size. Sol-gel technology is a well-established colloidal chemistry technology, which offers a simple process and at relatively low cost. Sol is a name of a colloidal solution made of solid particles few hundred nm in diameter, suspended in a liquid phase. The gel can be considered as a solid macromolecule immersed in a solvent. In general terms, the sol-gel process is the chemical transformation of a liquid (the sol) into a gel state. Sol-gel process has been used for glass coating since the 1939 and today it is a common technology for fabrication of ultra-fine powders, monolithic ceramics and glasses, ceramic fibers, inorganic membranes, aerogels and other types of materials [54-56].

Sol-gel technique is one of the most popular solutions processing for nanoparticles (mostly oxides) production [57,58]. This method is widely used in the production of oxide nanoparticles, given its low-cost and environmentally friendly character, coupled to the fact that it allows for the fine-tuning of several synthesis parameters [59]. The great control over the sol-gel process translates into the direct manipulation of the desired characteristics of the spinel product. The sol-gel method usually applies an organic mineralizer, which aids the incipient polymerization of the framework by complexing the cations involved in the process. Nano ferrites of composition $CoFe_2O_4$, $AlCoFeO_4$ and $Ba_{0.5}CoFe_{1.67}O_4$ have been fabricated by using sol-gel technique [60-62]

2. Experimental

2.1. Material

Al^{3+} substituted Cobalt ferrite with the chemical composition $AlCoFeO_4$ have been fabricated through sol-gel technique. Iron sulfate $[Fe(SO_4).7H_2O]$, Cobalt sulfate $[CoSO_4.7H_2O]$ are purchased from Merch, Aluminium

sulfate $[\text{Asl}_2(\text{SO}_4)3.16\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ from Rankam, Barium Sulfate $[\text{BaSO}_4]$ from Spectrum and Poly Vinyl Pyrrolidone $[(\text{C}_6\text{H}_9\text{NO})_n]$ from Sigma Aldrich were used as precursor materials. The precursors are of high purity (AR grade) hence, they have utilized in the synthesis process without any additional purification.

2.2. Synthesis procedure

Aluminium substituted Cobalt ferrite AlCoFeO_4 and Ba^{2+} substituted Cobalt ferrite $\text{Ba}_{0.5}\text{CoFe}_{1.67}\text{O}_4$ samples were synthesized through the sol-gel technique. The weighed amounts of the precursors were dissolved properly in the minimum quantity of deionized water required to get a clear solution (Figure a). The solution was heat treated along with continuous stirring on the hot plate magnetic stirrer at 80°C for 4 hours. During the heating process, the solution turned into the viscous gel (Figure b). The gel was then heated at 250°C for 2 hours has allowed combustion to take place. The dried gel burned in the combustion process until the entire gel was burned out to form a powder sample (Figure c).

Figure a

Figure b

Figure c

The resulting powder is crushed in an agate mortar to obtain the Nano ferrites. As prepared ferrite powder was annealed at 850°C for 6 hours to get single phase spinel product and used for further characterization. The step by step procedure for the synthesis of AlCoFeO₄ Nano ferrites by using sol-gel method is shown in the form of a flow chart.

By adopting this procedure, the following series of Al-Co Nano ferrites have been prepared at the annealing temperature of 1000°C for 6 hours [63].

3. Results and discussion

Spinel Ferrites of general formula AB₂O₄ finds application in different emerging fields like catalysts, selective gas adsorption and purification system, drug delivery, electrode materials for lithium ion battery, fuel cell, etc [64,65]. Most of the applications solely depend on the pore size and total surface area of the porous materials [66-70]. In this decade, ferrites were introduced as anode material for lithium ion battery to meet the high energy demands and the charge/discharge reactions of ferrite, as anode material, involves the formation and decomposition of lithium oxide (Li₂O), accompanying with the reduction and oxidation of metal nanoparticles [71,72].

In particular, anode material can enhance the capacity, which is even greater than the theoretical capacity of the respective anode material and also improves the charge/discharge rate capability of lithium ion battery [73].

Aluminum ion and Barium ion substitution by the replacement of Fe^{3+} ions in the ferrite system were also studied to compare the battery performance of pure and rare earth substituted ferrites as anode materials. The complete process was monitored through powder X-ray diffraction (XRD), scanning electron microscopy and energy dispersive X-ray spectrometer (SEM-EDS). The XRD patterns were recorded by using diffractometer with $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ radiation of wavelength 0.15460 nm from 20° - 80° . The particle size and morphology and elemental mapping and spectrum results of the prepared samples were obtained using Hitachi SN 3400N SEM. The powder samples were sprayed over conducting carbon tape and conducting carbon was sputtered over the sample and it was used for SEM analysis. The present chapter completely describes the simple and effective way of preparing porous ferrites as well as Aluminum ion and Barium ion substituted ferrites and their characterization results.

3.1. Powder X-ray diffraction of CoFe_2O_4 , AlCoFeO_4 and $\text{Ba}_{0.5}\text{CoFe}_{1.67}\text{O}_4$ nanoparticles

The formation of cubic crystalline structure of CoFe_2O_4 , AlCoFeO_4 and $\text{Ba}_{0.5}\text{CoFe}_{1.67}\text{O}_4$ was observed from the figure. Cubic crystalline structure of CoFe_2O_4 well matches with the XRD patterns reported with JCPDS (# 22-1086) of CoFe_2O_4 constants.

The Powder X ray diffraction patterns of CoFe_2O_4 , AlCoFeO_4 and $\text{Ba}_{0.5}\text{CoFe}_{1.67}\text{O}_4$ sintered at 1000°C for 6 hours were shown in Figure. The observed diffraction patterns of Aluminum ion and Barium ion substituted CoFe_2O_4 samples show the diffraction patterns correspond to the cubic CoFe_2O_4 crystalline phase, which was

confirmed by comparing the observed diffraction patterns with standard JCPDS (# 22-1086) data. All the samples show cubic structure, indicating the doping elements have been substituted into the structure successfully. All samples were confirmed by XRD to consist of a single phase of cubic structure thus showing that the dopants replace Fe without significant change of structure. The small peak shifts showed that the cell parameters changed along with the doping element. The substitution of small quantity of Aluminum ion (Al^{3+}) in place of Fe^{3+} slightly shifts the diffraction peaks of CoFe_2O_4 towards the lower angle and the substitution of small quantity of Barium ion (Ba^{2+}) in place of Fe^{3+} slightly shifts the diffraction peaks of CoFe_2O_4 towards the higher angle and it varied according to the d spacing. The d spacing values are affected by incorporating the ionic radius Al^{3+} and Ba^{2+} cation in the octahedral sites which shifted the oxygen ions surrounded over cation outwards with the expense of oxygen movement towards the tetrahedral holes [74].

The substitution of Al^{3+} and Ba^{2+} does not produce any patterns corresponding to $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Ba}_2\text{O}_3$. Instead, the substitution of smaller radius Al^{3+} (0.535 Å) in place of Larger radius Fe^{3+} (0.645 Å) ion decreases the lattice parameter from 8.354 Å to 8.349 Å. Also the substitution of larger radius Ba^{2+} (1.35 Å) in place of smaller radius Fe^{3+} (0.645 Å) ion increases the lattice parameter (a) from 8.354 Å to 8.360 Å.

3.2. Scanning electron microscopy and Energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (SEM-EDS) of CoFe_2O_4 , AlCoFeO_4 and $\text{Ba}_{0.5}\text{CoFe}_{1.67}\text{O}_4$.

The SEM images of CoFe_2O_4 , AlCoFeO_4 and $\text{Ba}_{0.5}\text{CoFe}_{1.67}\text{O}_4$ sintered at 1000°C for 6 hours in different magnification were shown in figures 1, 2, 3. Cobalt ferrites obtained from gels consist mostly of large agglomerates. The influence of the doping amount non uniformly distributed particle has been seen. Some moderately agglomerated particles forms big particles along with separated particles are also present in the image. It is evident by very large value of Coercivity, which is typical for agglomerated magnetic nanosystems. SEM images show a uniform but agglomerate surface of cobalt ferrite nanoparticles. Hence we have also reported coalesce of grains is higher at higher annealing temperature, which is also indicated from these micrographs. Because of the very small size of the crystallite, it was not possible to focus the electron micro diffraction analysis on a single metallic or spinel particles. Comparing the SEM images of CoFe_2O_4 , AlCoFeO_4 and $\text{Ba}_{0.5}\text{CoFe}_{1.67}\text{O}_4$, the grains of AlCoFeO_4 are fused more than other compounds proves that the conductivity will be increased by replacing Fe^{3+} by Al^{3+} in CoFe_2O_4 . Hence this behavior can be helpful in reduction and oxidation of metal nanoparticles which in turn can enhance the capacity of anode material.

Figure 1. SEM images of CoFe₂O₄ sintered at 1000°C for 6 hours at 5µm and 50 µm.

Figure 2. SEM images of AlCoFeO₄ sintered at 1000°C for 6 hours at 5µm and 50 µm

Figure 3. SEM images of Ba_{0.5}CoFe_{1.67}O₄ sintered at 1000°C for 6 hours at 5µm and 50 µm

The EDS values of CoFe₂O₄, AlCoFeO₄ and Ba_{0.5}CoFe_{1.67}O₄ were shown in Table. The EDS results confirmed the presence of Co, Fe, O, Al and Ba elements in the corresponding samples.

Composition	Element	Atomic %
CoFe ₂ O ₄	Co	32.45
	Fe	19.30
	O	39.7
Ba _{0.5} CoFe _{1.67} O ₄	Co	32.45
	Fe	19.30
	O	39.7
	Ba	8.55
AlCoFeO ₄	Co	16.25
	Fe	19.71
	O	43.47
	Al	11.62

Conclusions

In summary, the CoFe₂O₄, AlCoFeO₄ and Ba_{0.5}CoFe_{1.67}O₄ anode materials for advanced lithium storage have been successfully prepared by a Sol-gel technique. The Compounds under investigation were successfully synthesized and the effect of doping on the structure and microstructure has been analyzed using Powder X-ray Diffraction, Scanning Electron Microscopy and energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy. All the compounds confirms the stable cubic structure by XRD showing that the dopants doesn't create any significant change in structure. The substitution of small quantity of dopant (Al³⁺ and Ba²⁺) in place of Fe³⁺ slightly shifts the diffraction peaks of CoFe₂O₄ towards the lower and higher angle respectively. Instead, the substitution of smaller radius Al³⁺ (0.535 Å) in place of Larger radius Fe³⁺ (0.645 Å) ion decreases the lattice parameter from 8.354 Å to 8.349 Å. Also the substitution of larger radius Ba²⁺ (1.35 Å) in place of smaller radius Fe³⁺ (0.645 Å) ion increases the lattice parameter (a) from 8.354 Å to 8.360 Å. Comparing the SEM images of CoFe₂O₄, AlCoFeO₄ and Ba_{0.5}CoFe_{1.67}O₄, the grains of AlCoFeO₄ are fused more than other compounds proves that the conductivity will be increased by replacing Fe³⁺ by Al³⁺ CoFe₂O₄. Hence this behavior can be helpful in reduction and oxidation of metal nanoparticles which in turn can enhance the capacity of anode material. The EDS values of CoFe₂O₄, AlCoFeO₄ and Ba_{0.5}CoFe_{1.67}O₄ confirm the presence of Co, Fe, O, Al and Ba elements in the corresponding samples. Pure and composite ferrite Aluminum as anode materials in the form of nanoferrites have large surface area can give improved battery performance at high current rate. These compounds demonstrate the great potential for applications in energy storage. The synthetic effects of all components result in the enhancement of lithium storage performance through accelerating the electron/ion transfer and increasing the structural and interfacial stability.

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